

**TO EXPLORE HOW THE ONLINE AVAILABILITY OF KNIVES MAY
INFLUENCE KNIFE CARRYING AMONG 18-25-YEAR-OLDS IN ENGLAND AND
WALES.**

ABSTRACT

This study explores how the online availability of knives may influence knife carrying among young adults aged 18–25, a demographic often overlooked in existing knife crime research. Drawing on criminological theory and contemporary policy debates, the research addresses a gap in the literature concerning the relationship between digital access to weapons and carrying behaviours. A quantitative, cross-sectional research design was employed, using a self-completion survey online. A total of 14 participants contributed data, which was analysed descriptively and thematically. The findings indicate a strong consensus among participants that online access to knives increases the likelihood of knife carrying. Key motivations identified include gang involvement, peer influence, and self-protection, aligning with established theories. Participants highlighted significant concerns regarding the effectiveness of current safeguarding measures, particularly weaknesses in age verification processes and limited awareness of existing legislation. Overall, the study suggests that knife carrying is shaped by a combination of social, structural, and digital factors. It concludes that current legislative approaches may be insufficient without improved enforcement and greater regulation of online platforms, highlighting the need for more inclusive responses.

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Knife crime continues to be a pressing social and criminal justice issue across England and Wales. Within the British law, knife crime can be defined as crime involving a knife or sharp object, such as carrying the weapon with intent to harm, or using it to threaten or hurt others (Allen & Audikas, 2019, cited in Browne et al., 2022). Although the factors that contribute to weapon carrying vary in context, there is a growing concern over the accessibility of weapons through online retailers, which poses new risks to young people that are not yet fully understood. “Between April 2013 and June 2024, the number of selected offences involving a knife increased by approximately 91.5%” (ONS, 2024, cited in Home Office, 2025a). This statistic shows the urgency of examining the role of online knife sales, as this constitutes a safeguarding issue where young people are at risk of harm due to increased accessibility to weapons. As a result of understanding these factors, informed targeted interventions and policy responses can be aimed successfully at preventing knife-related harm amongst young people.

Research Aims

1. To analyse how online access to knives influences young people’s involvement in knife carrying.
2. To identify and examine the motivations for knife carrying.
3. To identify the safeguarding risks associated with young people’s access to knives through online platforms.
4. To evaluate current legislation and safeguarding regulating online knife sales.
5. To identify gaps in current safeguarding practices.

Rationale

There is limited understanding of online knife sales and how young people access knives through digital platforms (Home Office, 2025a). Most existing research focuses on social and environmental causes, such as gang involvement and deprivation (Goldson, 2011). This leaves significant gaps in knowledge regarding digital pathways that facilitate knife carrying and the public perceptions of online knife sales. Without this perspective, interventions may fail to reflect young people’s realities, limiting their effectiveness. My motivation for this study stems from personal experience as a victim of knife crime, which shaped my perspective on issues of safety and justice. This study will provide evidence to inform interventions and guide policy reform and is an opportunity to transform my personal experience into meaningful action, contributing to both academic knowledge and practical solutions in the field of crime prevention.

Chapter Two reviews the existing literature on knife crime among young people, highlighting key social, structural and individual factors, with criminological theories being used to explain knife

carrying motivations. The literature consistently shows young males as the demographic group most affected. However, a key gap is the limited research on online knife sales and how digital platforms enable access to weapons and the limited focus on 18–25-year-olds, justifying the need for this study.

Chapter Three details the methodology of this study and the data analysis approach. Chapter Four then presents the findings with a detailed analysis. The findings show strong agreement among participants that online access to knives increases the likelihood of knife carrying. Participants perceived knife purchasing online as relatively easy, highlighting the concerns around weak age verification and many reported encountering illegal or unsafe knife sales online. Overall, respondents viewed current legislation as ineffective, with low awareness of legislation.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

To address the aims of this study, the literature review focuses on dominant themes relevant to how online knife sales may influence weapon carrying among young people. This review is crucial to link the research question and findings to existing studies, demonstrating credibility and the contribution of my research (Bryman, 2012). Whilst this literature focuses on minors aged 13-17, this study instead examines 18–25-year-olds to explore whether online knife availability continues to influence carrying beyond the age of legal protection.

The Prevalence

1.1: Demographic Patterns and Trends

Weapon-related crime has remained a significant concern in England and Wales over recent years (Haylock et al., 2020). The Local Government Association (2019) note that knife crime has risen by 59% in England and Wales within the past five years, and there were 53,000 offences involving a sharp instrument in the year ending March 2025 (Allen & Wong, 2025). A substantial body of literature consistently indicates that young males are the demographic group most affected by knife crime, as both victims and offenders (Turner & Brahams, 2025). Bailey et al. (2020) indicate that knife-related offending is concentrated among 13- to 24-year-olds, with Browne et al. (2022) highlighting that males are most at risk of involvement in knife violence. The Ben Kinsella Trust (2024) reinforces this pattern, reporting that 57 young people under the age of 25 were murdered with a knife between March 2023 and March 2024. Similarly, 82% of teenage homicides involved a knife (Godbold, 2024).

1.2: The Dark Figure of Crime

The dark figure of crime is defined as occurrences that meet the criteria for being classified as crimes but are not included in the statistics (Biderman and Reiss 1967: 2, cited in De Castelbajac, 2014). A range of socioeconomic and contextual factors may discourage victims from reporting crime, which can distort our understanding of the true extent of crime (Baumer and Lauritsen 2010; Pezzella et al. 2019; Murvartian et al. 2023, cited in Fe, 2025). This suggests that reported offences may underrepresent the scale of possession and violence, thereby complicating attempts to evaluate the potential influence of online access to knives.

The Motivations

2.1: Gangs and Identity

Gang membership provides a sense of belonging and identity, which helps to explain why some young people join, particularly when social structures fail to offer recognition or purpose (Decker, 1996; Klein,

1971, cited in Matsuda et al., 2013). This aligns with Anderson's (1999) Code of the Street, which describes informal rules governing violence as a way to gain and maintain respect (Anderson, 1994, 1999, cited in Matsuda et al., 2013). Within this context, knife carrying can be understood as a strategy for achieving status in environments where societal pressures and no sense of belonging are persistent. Similarly, McVie (2010, cited in Browne et al., 2022) identifies higher rates of knife carrying among males highlighting the gendered risks of gang involvement. This gendered pattern can be understood through hegemonic masculinity, which is the dominant form of masculinity that legitimises male power and emphasises traits like toughness and dominance as key markers of male identities (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005). Within this framework, knife carrying may function as a way for young men to assert status, maintain respect, and avoid perceptions of weakness.

The Labelling Theory suggests that negative labels reinforces deviancy by shaping identities and internalising this, therefore increasing the likelihood of knife-related offending (Smith & Paternoster, 1990). In this context, the construction of 'gangster culture' can operate as a self-fulfilling prophecy, where individuals adopt and perform the identities that are being enforced (Hagedorn, 2008, cited in Clement, 2010). Although knife carrying is often associated with gang activity (Nacro, 2020, cited in Youth Justice Board, 2025), there could be an overreliance on gang involvement. Massey et al. (2019, cited in Alexander, 2023) found that only 21% of knife-related homicides were related to gang involvement. This indicates that while gang membership and street codes contribute to the motivations of knife carrying, knife accessibility may play a significant role in enabling weapon carrying beyond gang contexts.

2.2: Peer Influence

Barlas et al. (2006, cited in Haylock et al, 2020) report that self-identified weapon carriers consider peer influence as a paramount reason for weapon carrying. In support, Sawyer et al. (2018, cited in Firmin et al., 2022) highlight that young people become heavily influenced by peer relationships. Similarly, the Select Committee (2009;20-1, cited in Goldson, 2011) note that peer pressures can increase both weapon carrying and access to weapons. Sutherland's (1947) Differential Association Theory explains this through the learning of criminal behaviour where interactions with deviant peers results in the adoption of undesirable behaviours. Ultimately, this theory highlights the strong influence of social environment. Matsuda et al. (2013) state that peer exposure to gang-related violence can heighten violence among the group because it reinforces values favourable towards violence as a method to achieve and maintain respect. In the context of knife crime, peer modelling in digital spaces can amplify exposure to knife sales and normalise acquisition through online platforms.

2.3: Socioeconomic Factors

Neil (2007, cited in Squires, 2009) argues that weapon use within the community reflects the consequences of a 'broken society', highlighting socioeconomic factors as a key driver of knife crime. In support, Firmin et al. (2022) highlights that the harms young people face outside of their family homes are widely recognised as violence, demonstrating weapon-enabled violence as a safeguarding issue. Haylock et al. (2020) identify unstable social environments and deprivation as key predictors of knife carrying, with higher crime rates concentrated in economically deprived areas. In addition, Fagan & Wilkinson (2000, cited in Goldson 2011) argue that focusing solely on weapons as instruments of violence, detracts from the wider social ecology. This could result in particular young people becoming enmeshed in specific urban areas. Merton's Strain Theory supports this stating that deviance occurs when individuals are blocked from achieving valued goals through legitimate means, leading to frustration and alternative methods being sought (Murphy & Robinson, 2008). Shaw and McKay's Social Disorganization Theory (1942, cited in Sampson & Groves, 1989) proposes that social deprivation undermines the stability of communities, weakening their ability to maintain social organization and control. In these areas, social control is weakened and residents struggle to uphold the shared norms and values, therefore deviancy occurs.

2.4: Victimization

Eades et al. (2007; Traynor, 2016, cited in Youth Justice Board 2025) illustrate that knives are carried due to the fear of victimisation and the perceived and actual risk of victimisation is higher in gang members (Melde et al., 2009, cited in Bailey et al., 2020). Knife carrying is often perceived as a means of self-protection (Kemp, 2019), whilst some studies indicate that the majority of knife crime offenders have no prior victimisations (Bailey et al., 2020). Marfleet (2008, cited in Stephen, 2009) argue that when young people 'become streetwise' they view knives as a means of self-protection. Demographic factors intersect with victimisation, as Hindelang et al. (1978, cited in Zaykowski & DeCamp 2012) identify that black males from socioeconomically disadvantaged communities are most at risk of victimisation. The role of online knife sales can enable young people to acquire knives more easily for self-protection narratives.

Safeguarding Risks

3.1: Online Harms

Researchers predominantly focus on the positive effects of online environments, leaving the negative impact of social networking on young people underexplored (Keipi et al., 2017). Purba et al. (2025) argue that the rise in knife crime is a concerning example of unregulated digital spaces, where adolescents are increasingly vulnerable to harmful content online, such as knife sales, suggesting that exposure to this may encourage knife-related behaviour. Megele (2018) similarly emphasises the

content risks for young people online, noting the prevalence of harmful and age-inappropriate content. Luxton, June, & Fairall (2012, cited in Keipi et al., 2017) further highlight that online spaces can provide access to harm-advocating content, introducing additional risks. While these studies raise important issues, they largely rely on theoretical justifications and do not empirically measure whether knife carrying among young people is actually increased by exposure to online knife sales. This gap indicates a need for research investigating how online knife sales intersect with weapon-carrying behaviours among young people.

3.2: Age Verification and Delivery Risks

The UK government introduced the Online Safety Act 2023 to address a range of different online harms, including mandating age limits (Jarvie & Renaud, 2024). Similarly, the Offensive Weapons Act 2019 places significant responsibility on couriers to verify the age of recipients at the point of delivery, requiring a valid ID check (Home Office, 2025b). However, the case study of Ronan Kanda exposes that age verification failures are still persistent. The teenagers who murdered Ronan purchased knives online and collected them from the post office on the day of the attack without their ages being verified (Turner & Brahams, 2025). This case demonstrates a critical weakness in delivery procedures, where legal obligations are not always upheld, ultimately enabling under-18s to obtain knives and contributing to knife crime homicides.

Criminal Justice Responses

4.1: Legislation

Firmin et al. (2022) argue that the government fails to address the risks associated with young people and the impact this has amongst them. In addition, Turner & Brahams (2025) propose that the tightening of legislation is essential to tackling knife crime. Existing legislation, including the Criminal Justice Act 1988 and the Offensive Weapons Act 2019, prohibits the sale of knives to individuals under 18 and sets out strict guidance for online retailers, including age verification at delivery (Home Office, 2025a). In addition, the Online Safety Act 2023 seeks to make the internet a safe place for young adults, by tackling illegal and harmful content online (Schmidt, 2024). However, the legislation discussed here primarily focuses on protecting minors. As a result, individuals aged 18-25 fall outside of these restrictions, raising concerns about whether current legislation reduces online accessibility for this age group.

4.2: Preventative Approaches

The Home Office does not provide enough support and help to local trading standard teams to enforce breaches of knife sales legislation by online retailers (Local Government Association, 2019). Tougher sentencing has been introduced through the Violent Crime Reduction Act 2006, whereby the penalty

for possession of a knife in a public place was doubled from two to four years (Stephen, 2009). However, the number of organisations sentenced for underage sales of knives remains low (Sentencing Council, 2022). The ‘No Knives, Better Lives’ intervention has been linked to an 85% reduction in the number of individuals under 18 convicted of handling an offensive weapon (Skott & McVie, 2019, cited in Browne et al, 2022). Although these approaches demonstrate early intervention, their emphasis on minors highlights a significant gap in strategies targeting 18-25-year-olds, indicating that preventative strategies need to be adapted to address this demographic effectively.

Conclusion

The existing literature demonstrates that knife crime among young people is shaped by complex social, structural, and individual factors. A key gap in the literature is the lack of research examining the role of online knife sales in facilitating weapon carrying and there is little evidence linking exposure to online knife sales with actual knife carrying behaviours. Additionally, there is a notable absence of young person’s voice within the literature, which may overlook the lived experiences and motivations of young people themselves. Individuals aged 18-25 fall outside the primary focus of most preventative policies, despite being identified as a high-risk group for knife-related offending. As legal adults, this group can access knives freely, including through online platforms, yet little research explores how this accessibility influences such behaviour.

This study aims to address these gaps by focusing on the relationship between online knife accessibility and weapon carrying among 18–25-year-olds. By incorporating the perspectives of this age demographic, this research aims to contribute original insight into an underexplored idea, whilst also informing more effective and inclusive policy responses.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY AND ETHICS

Introduction

This research is positioned within the field of knife crime and online safety and explores how online availability of knives may influence knife carrying among young adults. This demographic is appropriate because young adults aged 18–25 represent a paramount, yet under-researched demographic in knife crime studies (Haylock et al., 2020), making their attitudes and perceptions valuable and relevant to the aims of this research. Existing literature lacks quantitative data directly from young adults. Their perceptions are significant because they provide an insight into how knife crime is understood, ultimately helping to address gaps in existing research and inform safeguarding responses. The study investigates the influence of online knife sales, explores the motivations for knife carrying and evaluates the safeguarding practices regulating online sales. A quantitative methodological approach was adopted to collect data on young adults' attitudes, which is descriptively and thematically analysed. This chapter outlines the chosen method, discusses the sample and distribution method, survey design, data analysis approach and the ethical considerations of the study.

Method

This study employs a quantitative research design to explore how online availability of knives may influence knife carrying. Primary data was collected from the public (Fallon, 2016), so that conclusions could be found from statistical findings (Greetham, 2015) and patterns could be identified (Bryman, 2012). The research project used a cross-sectional design, collecting data at a single point in time, which is suitable for analysing the measured variables (Fallon, 2016), such as motivations, laws and safeguarding risks. However, cross-sectional design has limitations, particularly in establishing casual relationships, which may affect the validity of findings (Bryman, 2012). This study employs an inductive approach, in which patterns are generated from the survey data, allowing theoretical explanations to emerge (Bryman, 2012).

The research instrument is a self-completion survey, including a mixture of open and closed ended questions, in which respondents answered questions by completing the survey themselves (Bryman, 2012). Self-completion surveys can be effective in gaining a clear overview and collecting data (Greetham, 2015). An advantage to this is that respondents can go at their own pace when considering their responses and this makes the overall picture of the situation clearer (Greetham, 2015). Surveys are appropriate because they can be distributed in large volumes, making them quicker to administer and reducing the cost (Bryman, 2012). On the other hand, surveys have their limitations. When simple questions are used it can limit the depth of response (Greetham, 2015). Generalization is a limitation because the findings from a non-representative sample may not be applicable beyond the specific

context of the study (Bryman, 2012). However, despite the disadvantages, surveys remain the simplest way of covering a representative sample (Greetham, 2015).

Sample and Distribution Method

The sample consisted of 14 respondents aged between 18 and 25 years old. This sample size reflects practical limitations including time and cost constraints, alongside the voluntary nature of participation through social media (Bryman, 2012). The sampling frame focused on individuals within this age group, aligning with definitions of emerging adulthood (Arnett, 2010). This ensured consistency with existing research and enhanced the relevance of the participants to the research aims. A non-probability convenience sampling approach was employed (Bryman, 2012), whereby participants were recruited through social media and voluntarily chose to participate. While convenience sampling can limit the generalisability of findings, this approach was chosen because it ensured access to relevant participants (Bryman, 2012). This was facilitated by the researchers' positionality, as their social proximity to the target demographic enabled easier recruitment.

The survey was distributed via Instagram to ensure that the target demographic was reached. The survey link was shared through an Instagram story, which included the eligibility criteria specifying that respondents must be aged between 18 and 25 years. As the survey link was publicly accessible, the total number of individuals exposed to the study is unknown. However, this method of distribution has its limitations. Using social media may result in under-coverage bias because only respondents with social media access can complete the questionnaire, which may reduce the representativeness of the sample (Bethlehem, 2010). Despite this, social media distribution was considered appropriate because young adults are represented among social media users, with 88% of individuals aged 18-29 reporting use (Smith, 2018).

The Survey

The research was conducted using a survey, which involved participants completing it online (Fallon, 2016), and was hosted on JISC, the LSBU-supported platform. The sections were structured around key themes including online influence, motivations, and safeguarding risks. The survey used both objective and subjective data (Vogt et al., 2014) and primarily used closed-ended questions, including nine dichotomous questions, to examine the difference in attitudes and opinions (Greetham, 2015). The survey questions were written to produce easily codable responses (Vogt et al., 2014), to enhance the comparability of responses (Bryman, 2012). However, to avoid restricting respondents' answers, one open-ended question was included, to allow respondents to freely answer the question in their own words, to provide more detailed responses (Dillman et al., 2014). The combination of question types allows for both quantitative measurement and qualitative insights (Bryman, 2012).

The measurement scale used was Likert scales, allowing responses to be pre-coded, making it easier to analyse (Bryman, 2012). Self-developed survey questions were devised to ensure that the questions directly related to the research question and addressed the research aims (Bryman, 2012). The questions relating to motivations for knife carrying were informed by criminological theories, including Anderson's (1999) Code of the Street and Sutherland's (1947) differential association theory. The questions on online safeguarding were informed by the Online Safety Act 2023 and the case study of Ronan Kanda. In this quantitative study, validity was ensured by recruiting the participants involved and designing questions that directly reflected the research aims, to ensure that the study measured what it intended to measure (Winter, 2000; Flick, 2009, cited in Cohen et al., 2018). The questions have content validity because they address the research question directly (Vogt et al., 2014). Reliability was addressed through the use of structured questions to promote consistency across responses (Bryman, 2012).

Data Analysis

Data analysis allows the researcher to make sense of the data gathered (Bryman, 2012). The findings are presented and analysed to evaluate and discuss the related themes from the literature review. In order to analyse the quantitative data, the results are presented using the method of horizontal bar charts, conducted by JISC platform, to effectively highlight trends (Greetham, 2015). When the closed-ended questions were constructed, the answers were pre coded (Vogt et al., 2014), which makes the processing of this data easier (Bryman, 2012). Horizontal bar charts were considered the most appropriate method because they are easy to interpret and understand (Bryman, 2012). The data was then descriptively analysed to determine mean scores and percentages, and this was appropriate because the study aimed to describe patterns in the data rather than test statistical significance (Bryman, 2012). The qualitative data was examined to extract core themes and identify patterns (Bryman, 2012). The qualitative data collected was thematically analysed and this allowed patterns and themes within participants responses to emerge (Bryman, 2012). The results link to the research question by providing an original insight into the relationship between online knife sales and knife carrying and inform more effective and inclusive policy responses.

Ethical Considerations

A signed medium-risk ethics form has been submitted. This study involves a potential for psychological stress for participants, as the survey concerns a sensitive topic which could cause distress. To minimise this risk, participants were provided with an informed consent form outlining the nature of the study (Bryman, 2012) and states the right to refuse to take part or to withdraw once the research has begun (Cohen et al., 2018). Similarly, there is a risk of emotional impact as a researcher (Dickson-Swift et al., 2008) because engaging with sensitive material may cause emotional distress. This risk will be managed by appropriate support from my supervisor and taking breaks when needed. Reflexivity is another key

ethical consideration. The researcher plays a central role in the interpretation of data and personal experiences may influence the design of survey questions and analysis of data (Finlay, 2002). This risk is minimised by practicing critical reflection. Confidentiality and anonymity are maintained by securely storing the data using LSBU OneDrive and ensuring that participants are not identifiable in the findings (Bell & Waters, 2018). In a survey, a participants privacy is guaranteed, thus anonymity is ensured (Cohen et al., 2018).

Conclusion

In summary, this study adopts a quantitative, cross-sectional design using self-completion online surveys to examine how online knife availability may influence knife carrying. A convenience sample of 18–25-year-olds was recruited via Instagram, which targeted the sample effectively. The use of primarily closed-ended questions and Likert scales were used to provide comparable data, whilst a qualitative open-ended question adds contextual ideas. Descriptive and thematic analysis methods were used to identify themes and patterns. Ethical considerations, including informed consent, anonymity and reflexivity were addressed. Overall, this approach is most appropriate in providing an analysis for the findings chapter.

CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

Introduction

This chapter presents and analyses the findings from the data collected to address the research aims outlined in Chapter One. The data was collected using a survey with fourteen participants and was analysed descriptively and thematically. The findings are organised according to criminological themes within the knife crime topic, with quantitative and qualitative data supported by participant quotations.

Online Access and Influence

Figure 1: Participants' level of agreement with the statement that online access to knives increases the likelihood of knife carrying among young people.

Figure 1 illustrates that all survey respondents (100%, n=14) agreed that online access to knives increases the likelihood of young people carrying knives. Of these, 64% (n=9) reported that they *strongly agree*, while 36% (n=5) indicated that they *somewhat agree*. This distribution indicates a highly shared belief and strong agreement among participants. As suggested by Purba et al. (2025), unregulated digital spaces can provide a space for harmful content to expose individuals to knife sales and therefore encourage deviant, knife-related behaviour. Similarly, Megele (2018) highlights the content risks online, which can introduce additional risks to young people being exposed to harmful material, including content that may facilitate knife carrying. However, while the data indicates a shared perception among respondents, it does not establish a casual relationship between online access and knife carrying behaviour. Therefore, further research is required to explore how online knife sales directly intersect with knife-carrying behaviours among young people.

Motivations for Knife Carrying

Figure 2: Participants' responses on the perceived motivations for knife carrying.

The data in Figure 2 illustrates the perceived factors influencing knife carrying. The most commonly selected factor was gang involvement (86%, n=12) followed closely by peer influence (79%, n=11), with self-protection being identified by a majority of respondents (64%, n=9). In comparison, socioeconomic factors and victimisation were less frequently selected (both 43%, n=6). Overall, the findings indicate that societal influences are perceived as the most significant drivers of weapon carrying, alongside self-protection.

These findings support Anderson's (1999, cited in Matsuda et al., 2013) Code of the Street theoretical framework, as the code provides a rationale for violent behaviour to occur in an approved way. In this context, weapon carrying becomes a practical way for individuals to sustain violent behaviour and deter the risk of potential threats. This aligns with the participants' views, as the responses suggest that gang membership may increase the perceived necessity of knife carrying. Similarly, Sutherland's Differential Association Theory explains the influence of peers through the social learning of criminal behaviour by the interaction with deviant peers, whereby individuals adopt values and attitudes that support offending (Sutherland, 1947). These findings align with previous research demonstrating that exposure to gang peer groups, who model violent behaviour, can heighten violence (Matsuda et al., 2013). This can amplify the normalisation of the exposure to knife carrying. Peer influence may not only increase the likelihood of knife carrying but also contribute to its social normalisation within certain contexts.

Self-protection was identified by the majority of respondents (64%, n=9) and Kemp (2019) highlights that knife carrying is perceived as a means of self-protection. Marfleet (2008, cited in Stephen, 2009) points out that when young people become street wise, they view knives as a means of self-protection, meaning that online knife sales enable young people to acquire knives easily for self-protection narratives. Qualitative data from *Participant #2* shows that "social isolation may result in the search for weapons during moments of distress" and this can be understood from a situational crime perspective. Crime is conceptualised as purposive behaviour designed to meet needs such as status and protection

(Clarke, 1995). In this context, knife carrying may be viewed as a rational choice response to perceived risks and rewards within peer environments, especially in environments where status and self-protection are highly valued. However, this perspective can be seen as a limitation when applied to the present findings, as it underplays the influence of socialisation processes identified by Sutherland (1947) and Anderson (1999), where behaviour is shaped through peer networks and shared cultural norms.

Figure 3: Participants' perception of the prevalence of knife carrying among 18-25 year olds.

The data in Figure 3 indicates that participants commonly perceive knife carrying among 18-25-year-olds as prevalent, with 50% (n=7) stating it is *somewhat common* and 21% (n=3) stating it is *very common*. In contrast, 21% (n=3) believe it is *not very common*, while one participant (7%) stated *do not know*. These findings reflect similar patterns of Bailey et al. (2020) who indicates that knife-related offending is concentrated among 13- to 24-year-olds. The Ministry of Justice data further indicates that 83% of knife crime offences in the year ending March 2024 concerned those over the age of 18 (Youth Justice Board, 2025), suggesting that young adults constitute a significant proportion of those involved in knife crime offending. These findings are relevant to this study as they highlight that individuals aged 18-25 are widely perceived as a critical demographic in relation to knife crime involvement.

Safeguarding Risks Online

Figure 4: Participants' perception of the ease of purchasing knives online without age verification.

The data in Figure 4 shows that the majority of participants perceived it to be relatively easy for young people to purchase knives online without age verification. Specifically, 43% (n=6) of respondents stated that it is *somewhat easy*, while 36% (n=5) believed it is *very easy*. A smaller proportion of participants were *neutral* on the issue (14%, n=2), while only one respondent (7%) felt that it is *very difficult*. No participants selected *somewhat difficult* (0%, n=0). Overall, these findings suggest that participants perceive online purchasing without age verification to be relatively easy, which may indicate limited confidence in the effectiveness of these safeguards.

These perceptions are further reflected in the qualitative data. *Participant #1* stated that there is a need for “monitoring social media and age restrictions for accessing the websites”, while *Participant #2* highlighted that “many online retailers lack robust age-verification systems and without proper age verification, knives can be bought quickly online”. Similarly, *Participant #3* emphasised simply the need for “more age verification”, collectively indicating a need for stricter regulations of online purchasing controls. In support of these views, Turner and Brahams (2025) note that retailers are required to implement a two-step verification process for online knife sales. Furthermore, *Participant #4* stated that there are “multiple ways of confirming the person of purchase is allowed to buy knives as well as age checking in multiple ways to minimise purchases for the wrong reasons”. Turner and Brahams (2025) also highlight that retailers are required to report bulk orders and suspicious activities to the police, reinforcing the importance of strengthened age verification monitoring.

Figure 5: Participants' responses indicating whether they have observed unsafe or illegal sales on social media, online marketplaces or other digital platforms.

The data in Figure 5 shows that 50% (n=7) of participants reported that they have *occasionally* come across unsafe or illegal sales of knives on digital platforms. In contrast, 29% (n=4) of respondents said that they have *never* encountered such sales, while 21% (n=3) indicated they were *not sure*.

These findings are situated within ongoing policy efforts to address the issue of online knife sales. The UK government established the Anti-Knife Crime Coalition, which aims to ban knife-related sales through social media (Purba et al., 2025). The Home Office (2024) also further states that the government plans to strengthen legislation around the online sales of knives, with the aim of reducing

access to dangerous weapons by young people. Similarly, the police are given powers to issue Content Removal Notices to online platforms and marketplaces that fail to remove illegal content relating to the sale of knives (Home Office, 2025b), highlighting a need for this legislation to be tightened. The qualitative data further reflects participants' views on measures relating to the prevention of unsafe or illegal knife sales on digital platforms. *Participant #2* stated that “retailers and platforms have a duty of care to prevent illegal sales”, proposing that online retailers must regulate the safety of young people. *Participant #6* proposed “a clearer reporting tool on social media and websites for when people try to purchase and sell knives so that it flags up suspicious sales and gets reported to the police”, suggesting the use of reporting mechanisms as a potential control measure. *Participant #9* suggested to “block all websites on UK phones selling swords and knives that couldn’t be used for kitchen use”, relating to the restriction of online access to sales platforms.

Legislation and Safeguarding

Figure 6: Participants' awareness of the laws regulating online knife sales.

The data in Figure 6 shows that the majority of participants are not aware of the current laws regulating online knife sales. 36% (n=5) reported that they were *not aware at all* and 29% (n=4) said that they were *not very aware*. In contrast, 36% (n=5) of participants stated that they were *somewhat aware* of the laws. Overall, the results show an even split between those with some awareness and those with little or no awareness, with no clear majority demonstrating strong awareness of legislation.

Figure 7: Participants' opinions on whether the current laws adequately prevent young people from accessing knives online.

The data in Figure 7 shows that 57% (n=8) of participants said that the current laws do *not at all* adequately prevent young people from accessing knives online. In contrast, 36% (n=5) said that laws are only *partially* effective, while one participant (7%) *did not know*.

These findings indicate a perceived gap in the effectiveness of existing legal frameworks regulating online knife sales and this gap is particularly significant when interpreted alongside the role of social networking platforms. Keipi et al. (2017) argues that the negative impact of social networking on young people remains underexplored, particularly regarding exposure to harmful content and access to illicit weapons. Social media platforms can facilitate the advertisement and informal sale of weapons, thereby potentially dismissing regulatory controls. In this context, Turner and Brahams (2025) argue that tightening legislation is essential to tackling knife crime; however, the present findings indicate that legislation alone may be insufficient if the influence and regulatory challenges of social networking environments are not also addressed. Together, this reinforces that the accessibility of knives online is shaped not only by legislative gaps but also by the affordances of social media platforms.

Similarly, the Home Office (2024) acknowledges this gap by proposing that legislation surrounding online knife sales needs to be strengthened to better prevent young people from accessing them. This is further reflected in data from the Sentencing Council (2022), which indicates that relatively few organisations have been prosecuted for underage knife sales. This points to a broader issue of enforcement deficits, where existing laws lack practical impact and effectiveness due to limited implementation. Consequently, participants' perceptions of legislative inadequacy may reflect not only gaps in the law itself, but also a lack of visible and effective enforcement within increasingly complex online spaces.

Gaps in Safeguarding Practices

Figure 8: Participants views on which areas require stronger safeguarding to prevent young people from accessing knives.

The data in Figure 8 shows that 50% (n=7) of respondents viewed *age verification upon delivery* as the most important area requiring stronger safeguarding to prevent young people from accessing knives online. Other areas were identified less frequently, with 21% (n=3) of respondents highlighting *age*

verification processes on websites, education and awareness. Only 7% (n=1) of participants identified *monitoring social platforms* as a key priority, making it the least selected option among those provided. One category received no responses (0%), indicating it was not considered a significant area for improvement. Overall, the findings emphasise a clear priority placed on strengthening age verification measures, alongside a more varied recognition of the need for improvements in implementation and education.

The Offensive Weapons Act 2019 places significant responsibility on couriers to verify the age of recipients at the point of delivery (Home Office, 2025), suggesting that safeguards are already formally in place. However, there is evidence that indicates that these measures are not consistently effectively implemented. The case study of Ronan Kanda illustrates this failure, as the perpetrators were able to purchase knives online and collect them from a post office on the day of the attack without any age verification at either point of sale or delivery (Turner & Brahams, 2025). This demonstrates a clear gap between legislation and enforcement because legal requirements are not upheld. This helps to explain why respondent may perceive current safeguards as inadequate and in need of strengthening. Participant's raised concerns around education and awareness, and this reflects broader structural issues. Significant reduction in youth funding and services have been cut by 73% (Turner & Brahams, 2025), which has contributed to the vulnerabilities among young people, and this could lead to an increased reliance on social platforms where the exposure to illicit goods is prominent.

The qualitative data further reinforces the perceived inadequacy of identity verification at the point of delivery as a prominent theme across participant responses. For example, *Participant #2* noted that "without strict ID checks at delivery, knives can end up directly in the hands of underage individuals", while *Participant #5* advocated for a "mandatory, strict two-step ID verification... at both sale and delivery". *Participant #7* echoed this concern by suggesting the "need for photo ID in person when delivering", and *Participant #8* stated that "all names should match on the ID... with the purchaser required to sign for the delivery". Collectively, these responses highlight a strong consensus that existing safeguards are insufficient, and that more robust age verification procedures are necessary to prevent access.

Conclusion

This chapter presented and analysed the key findings from a survey exploring young people's access to knives online, the motivators for knife carrying and perceived safeguarding measures and legislation. Overall, the findings indicate a strong consensus among participants that online access to knives increases the likelihood of knife carrying among young people. Across the findings, several key themes emerged. Participants consistently identified gang involvement and peer pressure as significant drivers of knife carrying, reflecting established criminological explanations such as Anderson's "Code of the Street" and Sutherland's Differential Association Theory. Alongside this, self-protection was also

widely recognised as a motivating factor, suggesting that knife carrying is understood by respondents as a rational response to perceived risk and vulnerability.

The findings highlight concerns around the ease of online knife purchasing and the perceived ineffectiveness of age verification processes, especially at the point of delivery. The data demonstrated a strong preference for stricter age verification processes. The participants' expressed a limited awareness surrounding knife-related legislation and a majority expressed that current laws are not adequately preventing access. Furthermore, the findings point to broader structural factors shaping these issues, including the role of online platforms in facilitating access to harmful weapons. Together, these factors suggest that knife-related risk cannot be fully understood through legislation alone, but must also be considered in relation to social, digital, and structural contexts.

Overall, this chapter demonstrates that participants perceive knife access online as shaped by a combination of weak enforcement, online accessibility, and social influences. The findings therefore highlight the need for a multi-layered response that incorporates strengthened regulations, stricter enforcement of current legislation and preventative interventions online.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION

This dissertation examined how the online availability of knives may influence knife carrying among 18–25-year-olds in England and Wales. The study was structured to explore this through existing literature, a quantitative survey, and analysis, with the aim of addressing gaps in knowledge surrounding digital access to weapons and its relationship with young adults' behaviour.

Chapter One introduced the topic by outlining the continued rise in knife-related offences across England and Wales and identifying growing concern around online knife sales. It set out the research aims and the rationale highlighted a significant gap in existing research, particularly regarding digital access to knives and the underrepresentation of 18–25-year-olds in knife crime literature. Chapter Two reviewed existing literature and demonstrated that knife crime is primarily explained through a combination of social, structural, and individual factors. Criminological theories such as the Strain Theory and Social Disorganisation Theory were used to explain the motivations for knife carrying. However, the literature revealed a consistent gap in understanding how online accessibility contributes to weapon access, particularly through unregulated digital spaces.

Chapter Three outlined the methodology used in this study. A quantitative cross-sectional design was employed using a self-completion survey online and the sample consisted of 14 participants aged 18–25. The survey included primarily closed-ended Likert-scale questions alongside one open-ended question to provide qualitative depth. Chapter Four presented the findings and analysis which showed unanimous agreement among participants that online access to knives increases the likelihood of knife carrying among young people. This reflects a strong perceived link between digital availability and weapon-related behaviour. The motivations for knife carrying align with established criminological theories which emphasises the role of social learning and identity in shaping behaviour.

Collectively, the findings show three key conclusions. First, online access to knives is perceived as a contributing factor to knife carrying among young adults. The study indicates that digital availability is seen as an enabling factor that interacts with existing drivers. Second, motivations for knife carrying remain strongly rooted in social context. Importantly, online availability reinforces these motivations by making knives easier to obtain when individuals feel threatened or influenced by peers. Third, safeguarding and legislative measures are perceived as insufficient. Participants consistently highlighted weaknesses in age verification systems and enforcement practices. The gap between legal requirements and implementation was particularly evident in relation to delivery processes. This suggests that the effectiveness of legislation may be undermined by enforcement failures and the complexity of regulating online environments.

Limitations of the Research

This study has several limitations. The most significant is the small sample size (n=14), which limits the ability to generalise findings to the wider population of 18–25-year-olds. The use of convenience sampling also introduces potential bias, as participants were self-selected through social media. The findings reflect attitudes and beliefs rather than confirmed patterns of knife carrying or purchasing. The cross-sectional design limits the ability to assess change over time or establish relationships between online access and behaviour. Finally, while the inclusion of an open-ended question provided some qualitative insight, a more extensive qualitative approach could have offered deeper understanding of individual motivations and lived experiences.

Recommendations for future studies

Future research should focus on more representative samples to improve generalisability. Longitudinal studies would also be valuable in examining how exposure to online knife content influences behaviour over time. In addition, qualitative methods could provide richer insight into how young adults interpret risk and safety in relation to knife carrying. Further research should also directly examine online platforms, including social media and marketplaces where knives may be advertised or sold. This would help to better understand the digital pathways through which access is facilitated.

The findings have several important implications for policy. First, enforcement of existing legislation, particularly age verification at the point of delivery, must be strengthened to ensure compliance in practice. Without effective enforcement, legal frameworks alone are unlikely to reduce access. Second, regulation should extend to include social media platforms and informal digital marketplaces, where enforcement is currently more difficult. Third, public awareness of knife-related legislation should be improved. Many participants demonstrated limited understanding of current laws, suggesting a need for targeted education campaigns aimed at young adults. Finally, preventative approaches should adopt a broader, multi-agency strategy that addresses social factors such as peer influence, identity formation, and perceived vulnerability, as well as the demographic of 18-25-year-olds.

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